

THE FORMATION OF PHONETIC COMPETENCE OF CADETS AT MILITARY INSTITUTIONS

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Nowadays, integration into the international education is becoming particularly relevant in the field of education, which contributes to rethinking the goals and objectives of learning foreign languages. Practical knowledge of a foreign language is a prerequisite for conducting successful professional activities in the context of modern social development, so professionally-oriented learning of a foreign language is given a leading role in developing methods for improving the level of professional language training of future specialists.

The problem of language training of a future specialists of a Military Institutions is significant, since the effectiveness of mastering information of a foreign language professional orientation depends on the degree of proficiency of cadets in a foreign language. Consequently, this leads to the need to develop skills of adequate understanding of terms and definitions in different professional fields, due to the increasing number of business communication with colleagues around the world.

The formation and improvement of foreign communicative activities of cadets of Military Institutions requires serious attention to aspects of learning the phonetic characteristics of professional speech, the development and perception of foreign language communication, the development of skills of oral communication, reading and comprehension of the material, because the success of speech depends on the clarity and expressiveness of the formalization of communication with the interlocutor. When studying a foreign language, the method of forming the phonetic competence of cadets of Military Institutions is understood as pronunciation training aimed at developing stable orthoepic skills of a foreign language in a professional direction for future specialists.

It is necessary to analyze the system of phonetic exercises and tasks aimed at forming and improving the pronunciation skills of professionally - oriented lexemes of cadets of Military Institutions when learning a foreign language. The authors of textbooks and manuals of a new generation on the study of foreign languages of military orientation believe that training in oral professional communication should be carried out by mastering all language skills (phonetic, lexical and grammatical) using various pre-text and post-text communication exercises. They, in turn, should be

compiled on the basis of verbal situations and aimed at forming and improving the correct pronunciation of professional lexical units of the language being studied, improving the ability to communicate and assimilate language material, understand the text, that is, all those skills that determine the successful participation of a modern specialist in a professional dialogue.

The formation of phonetic competence of cadets of Military Institutions is carried out due to the correct pronunciation of sounds and sound combinations, the implementation of orthoepic norms in speech activity, correct accentuation of words, possession of intonation means of speech expressiveness (tempo, timbre, voice strength, logical stress, etc.).

Systematic work to improve the pronunciation of professional lexemes is carried out by cadets throughout the course of learning a foreign language and is carried out on the basis of the principles of continuity of training, since the cadets learn the same foreign language in school, but the nature of improving their phonetic competence should change at different stages of training. From the very beginning, it would be advisable to repeat and systematize the rules of pronunciation, but the experience of working in groups of cadets of Military Institutions shows that it is often necessary to form it again for cadets, because groups are formed from graduates of different schools with a heterogeneous level of knowledge. Such a corrective course in phonetics requires significant time expenditures that are not provided for in the curriculum of the discipline.

Work on pronunciation in the process of learning a foreign language is of great importance for the development of oral speech skills, because the ability to understand a foreign language text is associated with the adequacy of the perception of the phonetic side of speech and the improvement of teaching foreign language speech activity is largely determined by the success of forming the pronounced foundations of this activity.

There are various approaches to teaching foreign language phonetics, but the most common are traditional and communicative approaches.

The essence of the traditional approach to the study of foreign language pronunciation is that learning should occur as a conscious assimilation of spoken actions and their acoustic effects. The development of auditory skills involves familiarizing yourself with the sounds of a foreign language, training their pronunciation and applying the acquired skills in speaking and reading aloud, and includes two types of exercises: active listening to the sample and conscious imitation.

The communicative approach to studying foreign language phonetics negates the traditional method, emphasizing that pronunciation training from the first classes should take place in real communication, and “pronunciation should” not be attached “to speech, but be its basis, inextricably linked with other components of teaching foreign language speech - lexical and grammatical skills”.

Therefore, it is necessary to combine traditional and communicative approaches when teaching the pronunciation of professional foreign language vocabulary to cadets of Military Institutions, since the use of only the traditional method is ineffective due to its focus on developing only acoustic and motor skills without taking into account the communicative aspect. The communicative approach, although based on communication, will not overcome the negative impact of interlanguage interference if it does not use the concepts of the traditional approach to form orthoepic skills.

REFERENCES:

1. Buginsky V. V. the Work on English pronunciation at the initial stages of communicative teaching foreign language speaking // ES, 1991. № 4. P. 43-45.
2. Pavlova S. V. Teaching foreign language pronunciation in a communicative-based // IES, 1990. № 1. S. 29-32.
3. Rogova G. V. Methods of teaching foreign languages in the secondary school / G. V. Rogova, F. M. Rabinovich, T. E. Sakharov. // Moscow: Prosveshchenie, 1991. 287 p.